

HISTORY OF STUDYING THE ANCIENT KESH CITY AND CULTURAL MONUMENTS

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Annotation: At the beginning of, Kesh had a great position in the Sogdian state. The Kashkadarya oasis became a crossroads of invasions in the 5th-7th centuries, and for some time the Kidaris, Chionis, and Ephtalians ruled this place. During this period, the Kang state began to exert its influence on the southern lands. Even Chorjoi is subject to him. The status of Kesh region will increase. It is also mentioned in the sources that it is included in the cache. This article provides information about the Kesh region based on sources.

Key words: Kesh, Ahurpat, Ahubido, Shorobsoy, Kitab, Oyokchisoy, Chimkurgan, Kizildarya, Tankhozdarya, Katagan, Kairagoch, Guldara, Langarsoy, Gavmurdin, Gishatepa, Sangirtepa, Uzungkir and Podayotoktepa.

The coins found in the Kesh area can also be of great help in shedding light on Kesh's political position in Sughd. The governor of the cache minted his own coins. Was the first to bring cash coins into the scientific process. I. According to Smirnova, the name, title of the ruler and the place where he ruled were written in Sugdian script on the reverse side of the Kesh coins . The researcher first read the name of the ruler as Akhurdat - "Akhura presented" and later as "Akhurpat"[1]. All numismatists consider the second word to be "ruler". For example D. Davidov also O. Agreeing with Smirnova's opinion, he connects the coins of Akhurpat with Kesh and based his opinion on the name of the governor of Kesh, Akhubido, who sent ambassadors to China in 727.

V.A. Livshits suggests reading the inscription on this coin as "Khokim of Akhurpat Kesh". As for the name of the rulers of Kesh known in written sources, comparing the inscription on the coins, this name can correspond not only to "Akhubido", but also to the name of Shi-Axe (Shir)-Ahura, who ruled in 656-660. Bronze coins were also found in the territory of Kesh region, from the period when the Sughd ikhshids ruled from Shishpir (642-656) to Turgar (738-750), but not all of them have been fully deciphered. He was executed in 751 during the reign of Abu Muslim. The felses issued by Ikhriddin, ruler of Kesh, date to the middle or second half of the 8th century. On the right side of them, the words "Ikhriddin Kesh farmer" are written in the Arabic alphabet, and on the reverse side, "This felse was minted in Kesh"[2].

The Arab author Yaqub cites the opinion that "the strengthening of Kesh's property begins at the beginning of the 7th century." The city rises to the level of the capital of the Sogdian state during these times. Socio-cultural relations with China will be established. The development of Kesh at the beginning of was closely related to the position of the Turkic Khanate. According to the sources, the ancient Kesh, which was built in the place of Kitab, remained in ruins even in the 10th century. The population moved to the south and gave the name Kesh to the new settlements they built. M. E. Masson concludes that the construction period of the city defense wall during the time of Amir Temur is 1378-1379.

In the eastern part of the oasis, 12 cultural economic districts related to ancient times are formed. These are Shorobsoy, Kitab, Ayokghisoy, Chimkurgan, Kyzildarya, Tankhozdarya, Qatagan, Qairaghoch, Guldara, Langarsoy, Gavmurdin, Gishatepa. Compared to the Early Iron Age, the number of settled areas in the oasis has doubled. In those days, the distance between the villages was not so far. The distance was 1.5 - 2 km. Villages in mountainous districts were 1-2 miles apart. The gap between individual districts did not exceed 7-9 miles. However, in the early Iron Age, the average distance between settlements was 7-22 miles.

Many of the ancient addresses have been lost without a trace. Only those settlements that were located in a place suitable for large-scale agriculture will continue to live in the following centuries. 27 out of 37 addresses in the Yakkabog district survived even in the II-VII centuries.

Irrigated agriculture appears in the highlands during the Early Iron Age. Guldara, located at the foot of Yakkabog Mountain, should be included in this list. Paykals were irrigated here with river water in the middle of the 1st millennium BC.

The study of Sangirtepa, Uzunqir and Podayotoqtepa monuments, which are considered to be the predecessors of the ancient city of Kesh, shows that these places occupied a position in. According to antiquarians, the period of the first formation of the Sangirtepa address, which is located on the bank of Shorobsay, one of the tributaries of Kashkadarya, corresponds to the 9th - 8th centuries. The sunken hill is 8 meters high and has a quadrangular shape. Its size is 85 x 65 meters. At that time, the southern and western sides of the monument were surrounded by fortification walls. Arki-Alo was built in the castle, the area occupied by it is 3 hectares.

650 m from Sangirtepa on the bank of Shorobsoy. in the north there is the Uzunqir monument. About 450 meters of the wall in the southwestern part of the hill has been preserved. The height of the wall reaches 6 meters, the base of the wall is amazingly thick 26 m. and consists of 3 lines. Pottery, animal bones, plant seeds were found in this place. In 1984, quilts, pottery, and ash layers were discovered. The age of this artefact is equal to the products of the 1st millennium. The site of the Uzunqir monument is 70 ha. covering the area, one of the largest cities of its time. In Uzunkyr, irrigation culture was high. Paykals are supplied with water from Shorobdarya and Zakhbuloksoy.

The monuments of Qalakontepa, Khontepa, Khojaqulitepalar also prove that the area around Kesh was crowded. A small iron knife and pottery vessels were found in these monuments. The lamps taken from Khontepa are attributed to the 12th century. The remnants of khums, khumchas, toro, pitcher, pot, lids, and mercury jugs are important material sources for illuminating the landscape of the period. Life in Khontepah continues continuously from the 6th to the 12th century.

In the centuries before Christ, there were many personal settlements in the highlands, riversides and lowlands of Kashkadarya oasis, where economic life and civilization were traced. This is also shown by the study of the monuments created in the middle stream of Kashkadarya - Chimkurgan water basin and its territory. At the beginning of the 50s of the 20th century, the construction of a dam and the foundation of a reservoir began on the Kashkadarya stream passing by the village of Chimkurgan (Qamashi district). The ancient monuments that remain at the bottom of the water basin are studied from the point of view of archeology in a rapid way.

The reservoir is 45 km away. In the circle of ², more than 20 monuments of the past are taken into account. When Ovultepa, Kindiklitepa, and Jangaltepa, which are submerged under water, are examined, ceramics from them, made in the middle of the first millennium, are obtained. A pottery kiln, a thin bowl, a plate, a bowl, and dates were found in Jangaltepa. The vessels show that cattle breeding and dairy farming were developing in Jangaltepa. Among the important finds are small nipples with nipples intended for feeding babies. The container has a hood, height is 9.6 cm, width is 5.5 cm.

There are also objects such as urchubosh, stone buttons, karakydon, yanchgich[3]. Sickles, small holes - iron objects came out of the site of Ovultepa. Ancient addresses are widespread in Kesh region. There are 38 locations in

Chirakchi district, 29 in Qamashi district, and 200 in Yakkabog district. Among the monuments belonging to the beginning of and the V-VII centuries, it is permissible to point out the addresses of Khuzar, Subakh, Iskifagn, Navqad-Quraysh, Qamaytepa, Altintepa, Gishatepa, Kishmishtepa, Chechaktepa, Sariqtepa.

At the beginning of the millennium, these places were villages where agriculture, animal husbandry and handicrafts were developed. During the excavations in Chechaktepa (/Yakkabog') 45 different vessels were found. 90% of dishes are machine-made, and 10% are made by hand. One of the unique items of ancient pottery is the tableware called "Dasturkhan". The size of ceramic tiles ranges from 35 cm to 80 cm. The table from Chechaktepa is also similar to its fellows [4].

Khuzor was also part of Kesh. There were many cities belonging to Khyzopra. Among them, Subakh and Iskifagn Eskibog took an important place. One of the towns subordinate to Kesh province is located in the middle of Navqad-Quraysh, Yakkabog and Qamashi districts, near the present village of Karabog. There are monuments of Qamaytepa and Altintepa in Qamashi district. One is located in the village of Chim, the other in the village of Kovchin. Gishatepa belonging to Yakkabog district, Kishmishtepa near the center of Chirakchi district are among the ancient cities according to antiquarians. The monument of Sariqtepa was created during the Turkish khanate. Its area is 240 m. consisting of ² [5].

By the 8th-9th centuries, life stopped in most of these settlements. Addresses are abandoned. It is correct to say that this is directly related to the Arab invasion that took place during this period. By the beginning of Christ, historically important political changes will take place in Central Asia. At the center of events are the Kidarians, Chionites and Hephthalites. In Chinese sources - the Bei-shi chronicle, for example, it is reported that the leader of the Yuezhi, tired of the Juzhan attack, moved his residence to the city of Bolo. In the chronicles, it is reported that after that, the brave ruler Tsidolo (that is, Kidar - the authors) of the Yuechi crossed the mountains and attacked northern India with his troops, subduing five countries.

The Kidaris, in terms of origin, were blood related to the Kushans / Yuechjis or from the peoples that were part of them. Historians consider the Khioni to belong to the Kidaris. The Kidaris and Khionids had launched attacks against the rulers of Sassanid Iran, bringing them to the brink of destruction. The struggle with the Ephthalites intensified during the reign of Feruz /459 -

484/. Feruz dies in battle. Battles also take place in the Vaalam area. The Kidarians, Chionians, and Ephthalites, who are related by blood, end Iranian rule. At the end of the 5th century, the Sassanids were forced to bow to the Hephthalites and pay compensation.

Thus, Kesh retains the weight of the main city of Sogd in the late 3rd and early 4th centuries, and thus also in the following centuries. According to the testimony of the historian Yaqub, Kesh began to grow stronger from the beginning of the 7th century. During this period, the governor of Kesh, Ticho /Fichje/ built the city of Tsishi /Ki-sheshe/. By sending ambassadors to neighboring countries, he strives to strengthen relations with them and increase the power of the Kesh region. Coins are minted. In the middle of the 7th century, Keshga Shisheppa /Shishpar/ becomes the king. During his time, Kesh continued to mint coins. The inscription "Ikhshid Shishpar" is written on the coins .

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